

**Open Research Case Study
Lancaster University**

**Building Open Research Infrastructure:
Establishing *The Journal of Practice
Theory* through Open Journal Systems at
Lancaster University**

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This case study outlines the development of *The Journal of Practice Theory* (JPT), the first international, peer-reviewed, open access journal to be published at Lancaster University using Open Journal Systems (OJS). The project demonstrates how open research practices can be embedded not only in individual outputs, but in the infrastructure that enables research to be shared more openly, equitably, and sustainably.

The journal was established to address a structural gap in the field of practice theory. While the area has expanded significantly across disciplines, it lacked a dedicated venue to connect theoretical, conceptual, and empirically grounded work. At the same time, the project was motivated by a broader commitment to open research: to make high-quality scholarship freely available, to remove financial barriers to publication, and to explore non-commercial, scholar and community-led models of academic publishing.

To realise this, we worked closely with Tom Morley and the Open Access Team at Lancaster University Library to implement OJS as a publishing platform. This represents a form of open research practice that goes beyond compliance: rather than simply making outputs open, the project contributes to building institutional capacity for open publishing. OJS was selected because it enables full editorial workflows (submission, peer review, production, and publication) within an open, institutionally supported environment. This introduction of the platform now enables Lancaster University to host and manage its own journals, rather than relying exclusively on external commercial providers. Several other journals have begun to make use of this Lancaster open access platform.

Open research practices were embedded throughout the journal's design. JPT is fully open access, with no author processing charges, ensuring equitable participation regardless of institutional or financial context. Articles are published with DOIs, structured metadata, and in both HTML and PDF formats to maximise discoverability and accessibility. Editorial processes are transparent and clearly documented, including policies on peer review, AI use, and publication ethics. The journal also supports diverse formats (including shorter, more accessible "columns"), extending engagement beyond conventional research articles.

The process of establishing the journal involved several challenges. These included developing editorial workflows within a new system, ensuring quality and credibility as a new publication, and aligning open access principles with the expectations of academic publishing. The support of the Library's Open Access Team was crucial in addressing these challenges, particularly in configuring OJS, advising on metadata and indexing, and supporting sustainable workflows. A further challenge was discoverability: open access alone does not guarantee visibility. In response, we have begun developing an indexing and search engine optimisation strategy (including applications to DOAJ and Crossref) to ensure that published work is both accessible and findable.

The outcomes of this project are both immediate and strategic. The [inaugural issue](#) of JPT has been published and is freely available worldwide, supporting the dissemination of research across disciplines and beyond academia. The journal has already begun to establish an international network of contributors, reviewers, and readers. Importantly, the project demonstrates that Lancaster can support high-quality, peer-reviewed, open access publishing using its own infrastructure, with extremely modest financial investment. The return on such investment is maximal.

The benefits extend beyond the journal itself. This initiative provides a model for developing further open access publications that can profile areas of research strength at Lancaster. It contributes to a more equitable publishing environment by removing paywalls and author fees, supports greater transparency in editorial processes, and enhances the University's reputation as a leader in open research and scholarly communication.

Several lessons have emerged from developing this project. First, developing open research infrastructure requires close collaboration between academic and professional services; the partnership with the Library has been central to success. Second, openness must be actively designed into workflows and policies; it is not achieved simply by making outputs free to read. Third, building a journal is also about building a community: sustaining reviewer networks, encouraging diverse contributions, and fostering shared ownership of the publication.

This case demonstrates that open research can be advanced not only through individual practices but through the creation of institutional infrastructures that enable new forms of scholarly communication. It highlights the opportunity for Lancaster to extend this model, supporting world-leading research areas through open, community-led publishing.